

Post-workshop Survey Questionnaire

* Required

1. Based on your experience with the LLM-based tool, please rate its ease of use in generating the RE artefact on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 signifies 'very difficult' and 5 signifies 'very easy'.

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1	2	3	4	5
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2. Do you have any additional insights into the ease of use in generating the RE artefact using the LLM tool? (Optional)

3. Considering your experience with the tool you used, please rate the ease of integrating it into your RE processes on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 signifies 'very difficult' and 5 signifies 'very easy'. *

1	2	3	4	5
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4. Do you have any additional insights into the ease of integrating the LLM tool into your RE process? (Optional)

5. "Considering your requirements engineering process, please rate the usefulness of the LLM tool on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 signifies 'not at all useful' and 5 signifies 'very useful'." *

1	2	3	4	5
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6. Do you have any additional insights into the usefulness of LLM assistance in generating the RE artefacts (optional)?

7. Based on your evaluation, please rate the quality of the artefact on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 signifies 'very low' and 5 signifies 'very high'.

1	2	3	4	5
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8. Do you have any additional insights into the the quality of the LLM-generated artefacts? (Optional)

9. Based on your evaluation, please rate the implementability of the LLM-generated artefacts on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 signifies 'very low' and 5 signifies 'very high'.

1	2	3	4	5
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10. Do you have any additional insights into the implementability of the LLM-generated artefacts? (Optional)

11. Reflecting on your experiences from the workshop, please rate the suitability the LLM tool for adoption into your RE processes for future projects.' on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 signifies 'not at all suitable' and 5 signifies 'highly suitable'.

1	2	3	4	5
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12. Do you have any additional insights into the suitability of LLM tools' adoption in your RE processes? (Optional)

13. On a scale of 1-5, 1 signifying total disagreement and 5 signifying complete agreement, to what extent do you agree that the concepts and techniques presented in the prompt engineering seminar adequately prepared you for the workshop?

1	2	3	4	5
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14. Do you have any additional insights into the adequacy of the concepts covers in the prompt engineering seminar? (Optional)

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